

Growth and Performance of Food Processing Industry in India

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Abstract: The food processing industry connects farmers to consumers through process of value addition to agricultural produce by enhancing their shelf life and quality. Based on the quality of inputs and value addition process, the products are marketed at domestic and international markets, thus contributing to GDP of the country. This industry is of significant importance to India since large population depends on farming for income generation, specifically rural areas. This paper is an attempt to analyse the growth of food processing industry in terms of employment and value addition. The research further probes into industry performance based on efficiency change and Total Factor Productivity Change over past ten years, that is, from 2008 to 2018. The Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) model which is non-parametric in nature is adopted to compute the efficiencies. The results indicate that there is increase in number of processing units while employment opportunity has shrunk. The empirical evidence suggests that the industry performed better during 2008-2013 compared to recent years. The value addition in food processing industry has tremendously amplified over years. In addition, the technical efficiency of food processing industry has increased while TFP change for overall industry shows decline.

Keywords: Efficiency Change, Total Factor Productivity Change, Value addition

I. Introduction

The food processing industry is gaining extensive importance with new emerging markets and technologies. In global economy, food processing has become an integral part of the food supply chain. In developing country like India, there exists high-growth and high-profit in this industry due to its immense potential for value addition, particularly within the food processing industry. Despite India being one of the largest producers of agricultural commodities in the world, agricultural exports as a share of GDP are fairly low in India relative to the rest of the world. India exports raw materials, which are then processed in other countries, again indicating the space to move up the value chain.

Post liberalization, processing of agriculture produce gained great scope for conversion into consumer commodities. The slow establishment of this process reduces wastage, increases shelf-life resulting in value addition. These agro products gained access to various classes of consumers by expanding market, thus generating high income to the farmers. However, processed food in India is still a niche market with huge potential growth. The Government of India has prioritized and initiated programmes to boost trade by value addition in agro- processing sector.

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Figure 1: Overview of Import and export of principle agricultural commodities in India

Source: Agricultural and Processed Food Products Export Development Authority, India

The Fig. 1 above depicts the import and export of agricultural commodities in India over the past decade. The import of agricultural produce is increasing over the years from Rs. 17,142.20 Crore in 2009-10 to Rs. 34,973.97 Crore 2018-19 which accounts to two-fold increase. On the other hand, export saw four-fold increase during five years from 2009-10 to 2013-14, and off late, started decreasing and has dropped by 5.8 percent in 2018-19 when compared to 2013-14. According to report of Agricultural and Processed Food Products Export Development Authority, India primarily exports basmati rice followed by buffalo Meat and non-basmati rice. Major imports of India are Fresh fruits followed by pulses and Alcoholic beverages.

Table 1: Average Annual Growth Rate (in Percentage) of Gross Value Added

Sector	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18
Manufacturing	7.96	4.97	7.9	13.06	7.94	5.93
Agriculture, Forestry & Fishing	3.45	5.57	-0.22	0.65	6.27	4.98
Food processing industry	8.41	0.39	2.66	20.55	10.76	7.68

Source: MoFPI, Government of India

The Table 1 above exhibits the Average Annual Growth Rate of Gross Value Added expressed in percentage by various sectors in India. The growth rate is high and is fluctuating over the years with least of 0.39 percent in 2013-14 to 20.55 percent in 2015-16. This indicates that the food processing industry contributes significantly to the country's GDP.

This paper is an attempt to analyse the growth of food processing industry in terms of employment and value addition. The research further probes into Efficiency Change and Total Factor Productivity Change. Section 2 presents literature review, research objectives, methodology and data collection. Section 3 explains the classification of food processing industry. Section 4 analyses the growth and efficiency of food processing in India, followed by Summary and conclusion presented in Section 5.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Prior studies have been conducted on various aspects of food processing industry in India.

Salama [2018] measured the level of efficiency of the state budget of agricultural sector in Indonesia using DEA approach. The outcome of the study indicates that during the year 2015 the realization of State Budget for agriculture sector is incompetent. In other words, the realization of state expenditures for agriculture is not balanced by significant results. Bhandari and Vipin (2016) analysed the efficiency and related technological aspects of the Indian food processing industry during 2000-2015 by collecting firm level data. The two aspects of the study are to measure technical efficiency of the individual production units of the industry and to appraise the extent of diverse technologies used across its various groups. The results indicated that dairy and sugar processing units had lower technical efficiency indicating opportunity to improve their overall performance to a sizeable extent through technological Upgradation.

The vegetable oil and products have high technical efficiency implying that improvement in overall performance is achieved through competent utilization of inputs.

Ohlan (2013) examined Efficiency and Total Factor Productivity Growth in Indian Dairy Sector over the period 1980-2008. From the research, it is found that there is an average technical efficiency level of 72%. Further, the decomposition of TFP growth indicates that growth is driven more by technical efficiency changes than by scale efficiency. It is argued that high volume of milk does not reach to milk processing plants for which plan of action has been suggested. Ajetomobi (2012) investigated Total Factor Productivity of agricultural commodities in the Economic Community of West African States using panel data of ECOWAS rice, cotton and millet production for the period 1961-2005. The productivity measures are decomposed into two sources of growth, namely efficiency change and technical change. The results for both SFA and DEA methods show evidence of phenomenal growth in total factor productivity for rice and cotton. Millet, however, has mixed results.

Swinnen and Maertens (2007) ventured to manifest the importance of changes in value chain and its implications. It was found in their study that farm profits were considerably higher which was achieved by lower production and marketing costs for contract farms compared to independent smallholders in schemes for milk, broilers, and vegetables in India. Kumar and Basu (2008) measured the change in technical efficiency and scale efficiency in the Indian food industry during the period 1988-1989 to 2004-2005 using data envelopment model. The research concludes that due to mediocre technology innovation entwined with ineffective use of inputs the industry is not able to operate at full fledge.

Singh, Tegegne and Ekenem (2012) analysed in detail the opportunities and challenges faced by Indian food processing industry. According to the study, the hope lies in holistic development of contemporary technologies such as electronics, material science, computer, biotechnology which offers vast scope for rapid improvement and progress. The availability of agricultural produce all through the year is an added advantage. However, lack of connection between R&D labs and industry coupled with competition from global players are hindrances. Milner, Vencappa and Wright (2007) evaluated the post performance of Productivity Growth in Indian Manufacturing due to policy changes. It has been found that the industries performed better with favourable growth of TFP post reformation in India.

Wilkinson (2004) addressed impact of the globalization in food processing industries in developing countries. The study identifies that opportunity for developing countries lie in exporting processed foods particularly in sea foods and fruit & vegetables. Mitra (1999) estimated the technical efficiency and total factor productivity growth for 17 two-digit industry groups considering 15 major states in India. The research deduces that the total factor productivity growth in most of the industries seems to have improved across many states during 1985-86 to 1992-93 when compared with period 1976-77 to 1984-85. It has been identified that Technology innovation, effective employment of inputs and improved infrastructure facilities have contributed in this regard.

2.1 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- I. To analyse the employment and value addition of food processing industry in India.
- II. To appraise the performance based on efficiency change and Total Factor Productivity Change of food processing industry over the past decade in India.

2.2 METHODOLOGY

The study is descriptive in nature. The food processing industry is classified into eight groups: Meat and meat products, Sea food, Fruit and vegetables, Vegetable and animal oils, Dairy products, Grain mill starches & starch products, other food products and Animal feeds for the purpose of study. The Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) model which is non-parametric in nature is adopted to compute the efficiencies. This model renounces the specification of the technology thus provides superiority in dealing with disaggregated input and output variables.

The study employs Malmquist productivity index to estimate the efficiency change and Total Factor Production change in the Indian food processing industry. The advantage of Malmquist index is that price inputs are not required and measures efficiency over time by computing the ratio of the distances of each data point relative to a common technology. The gross value of output represented by Products & By-products is considered and input is such as capital, labour, materials consumed and fuel consumed are considered. The Data Envelopment Analysis Program

(DEAP) software (version 2.1) developed by Coelli (1996) is used to compute the efficiency score and Malmquist Total Factor Production (TFP) index.

2.3 DATA COLLECTION

The research is conducted on secondary data collected from various issues of Annual Survey of Industries for a period of ten years (2008-09 to 2018-19). Group level data of eight categories Meat and meat products, Sea food, Fruit and vegetables, Vegetable and animal oils, Dairy products, Grain mill starches & starch products, other food products and Animal feeds are contemplated.

III. CLASSIFICATION OF FOOD PROCESSING INDUSTRY

The classification is based on Indian National Industrial Classification of 2008 as framed by Central Statistical Organisation.

a. Meat and meat products: This includes Mutton, Beef, Pork, Poultry and other slaughtering, preparation, preservation, processing and canning of meat, production of hides and skins originating from slaughterhouses, rendering of lard and other edible fats of animal origin, production and processing of animal offal and other meat and meat products.

b. Sea food: This includes Sun-drying of fish, artificial dehydration of fish and sea food, radiation preservation of fish, processing and preserving of fish crustacean, canning of fish, canning of frog legs and other fish products. Production of fishmeal for human consumption or animal feed.

c. Fruits and vegetables: Includes Sun-drying of fruit and vegetables, artificial dehydration of fruit and vegetables, radiation preservation of fruit and vegetables, manufacture of fruit or vegetable juices and their concentrates, squashes and powder, sauces, jams, jellies and marmalades, pickles, chutney, canning of fruits and vegetables, potato flour & meals and prepared meals of vegetables, preservation of fruit and vegetables.

d. Vegetable and animal oils: Manufacture of hydrogenated oil and vanaspati ghee, vegetable oils and fats excluding corn oil, Manufacture of edible animal oils and fats, fish oil, non-edible animal oil and fats, oil cakes & meals incl. residual products, Manufacture of non-defatted flour or meals of oilseeds, oil nuts or kernels.

e. Dairy products: Includes pasteurisation of milk whether or not in bottles/ polythene packs, Manufacture of milk-powder, ice-cream powder and condensed milk, baby milk foods, cream, butter, cheese, curd, ghee, khoya, ice-cream, kulfi and other dairy products. This excludes production of raw milk and activities in ice-cream parlours.

f. Grain mill, starches & starch products: Milling of Flour Rice, Dal (pulses) Grain milling other than wheat, rice and dal, roots or tubers, or of edible nuts, Manufacture of cereal breakfast foods obtained by roasting or swelling cereal grains, flour mixes and prepared blended flour and dough for bread, cakes, biscuits, readymade mixed powders like idli, gulab jamun. Manufacture of starches from rice, potatoes, maize, sago and sago products, glucose, glucose syrup, maltose, gluten, tapioca and tapioca substitutes prepared from starch, corn oil and other starch products.

g. Other food products: Manufacture of bakery products which includes bread, biscuits, cakes, pastries, rusks and other bakery products. Manufacture of sugar in which process it includes refining of sugar, gur, khandsari, boora and candy from sugarcane and other than sugarcane, and sugar from other sources such as juice of palm, beet etc. and molasses. Manufacture of cocoa, chocolate and sugar confectionery. Manufacture of macaroni, noodles, couscous and similar farinaceous products, Manufacture of prepared meals and dishes in frozen or canned form. Processing and blending of tea, Coffee curing; Roasting, grinding blending and coffee products, edible nuts, malted foods, papads, appalam and similar food products. Manufacture of vitaminised high protein flour, frying of dal and other cereals, processing salt into food-grade salt.

h. Animal feeds: This includes manufacture of cattle, poultry feeds, prepared feeds for pets, including dogs, cats, birds, fish and other animals.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Food Processing Industry has emerged as a pivotal segment of the Indian economy in terms of its contribution to GDP accompanied with employment generation. The industry connects farmers to consumers through process of value addition to agricultural produce by enhancing their shelf life and quality. Thus, industry is positively impacting farming community in generating income. On the other hand, the expanding consumer base due to rapid growth in population coupled with disposable income proffers potential benefits. The first section discusses the growth of Food processing industry in terms of number of processing units and employment generation at each group.

Table 2: Growth in Food processing industry at 5-year interval in India in past decade

Group	2008-2009	2012-2013	2017-2018	2008-2009	2012-2013	2017-2018
	No of factories			Employment (in thousands)		
Meat & meat products	90	140	180	22.13	26.94	14.55
Sea food	352	462	538	36.77	87.61	33.06
Fruit & vegetables	709	1110	1256	55.09	77.99	45.00
Vegetable and animal oils	2429	3312	3044	111.22	105.04	106.80
Dairy products	1100	1695	2064	135.11	176.96	102.25
Grain mill, starches& starch products	14052	18855	19587	322.85	370.35	346.78
Other food products	6577	8648	10174	825.29	855.21	762.79
Animal feeds	547	873	989	38.73	72.30	28.40
Food processing Industry	25856	35095	37832	1547.18	1772.40	1439.62

Source: Annual Survey of Industries, CSO, New Delhi

The Table 2 above depicts the number of processing and number of employees under each group over past decade with five-year interval. The overall number of factories in Food processing industries have increased by around 46 percent during 2008 to 2018. All the groups exhibits rise in number of factories except Vegetable and animal oils processing units have reduced by 8 percent from 3,312 units in 2012-13 to 3,044 units in 2017-18. The reason for decline in the unit is attributed to drop in the oilseeds production due to various issues such as low productivity and switching into other crops in recent years. Also, the imports to fulfil the domestic requirements at competitive prices accompanied by policy implementation to cut taxes have largely impacted.

Further, it is evident from the table 3 that the first five year of analysis duration constitutes better growth compared to the second half. The animal feeds processing units have increased by 60 percent manifesting highest growth during 2008 to 2013 while the sea food processing units had increased by around 31 percent displaying least growth. In the second half, from 2013 to 2018, meat and meat product processing units have raised by around 28 percent while Grain mill, starches and starch processing units have registered least growth of around 4 percent showing increase at diminishing rate. The overall scenario indicates that demand for meat and meat products has increased exponentially compared to other groups.

On the employment front, the total number of employees has shrunk by around 7 percent over the past decade (from 2008 to 2018) in Food processing Industry. The highest labour force is found to be in other food products category which employed around 8,25,290 employees in 2008 (labours and managers) and has reduced to 7,62,790 employees in 2018. On the rational grounds, technological innovations are held responsible because of which employees are substituted by automated machineries. Again, the trend of enormous employment opportunity persisted in the first five years of study (during 2008-13) except Vegetable and animal oils processing (employees reduced by 5 percent).

The stated reason in the previous section for tailing off Vegetable and animal oils processing units' holds well with consequent repercussions of downsizing the employees. At the second half duration of the analysis (during 2013-2018), all groups indicate sharp decline in employment except with Vegetable and animal oils processing increased by 2 percent. The sea food processing group lost major chunk of around 62 percent while Grain mill, starches & starch product processing laid down around 6 percent employees.

Figure 2: Estimated value addition under various in Food processing industry in India

Source: Annual Survey of Industries, CSO, New Delhi

From the above Fig. 2, it is evident that value addition in food processing industry has tremendously amplified over years. The animal feed processing has improved by 10-fold in the past decade which is highest amongst all groups while vegetable and animal oil processing have increased fairly by one and half times. The major contributors are other food products group which include four main sub categories such as Manufacture of bakery products, manufacture of sugar, and manufacture of prepared meals & dishes in frozen or canned form and Processing and blending of tea, Coffee followed by grain mill, starches and starch products processing group.

The next section discusses the cost and efficiency of food processing industry over the past decade in India. The cost structure is divided into four categories for the analysis. They are a) wages and salaries which represent the remuneration paid both labours and managers b) Fuel consumed which includes energy generated to process in terms of petrol, diesel and electricity c) Material consumed which indicates inputs such as raw agricultural produce, chemicals and d) packaging and cost of capital which is sum of depreciation, interest and rent paid.

Table 3: Comparison of cost structure (in percentage) in Indian food processing industry

Group	Wages and salaries		Energy Consumed		Materials Consumed		Cost of capital	
	2008-09	2017-18	2008-09	2017-18	2008-09	2017-18	2008-09	2017-18
Meat and meat products	3.61	8.26	40.41	19.18	53.40	68.20	2.58	4.37
Sea food	2.98	3.54	3.67	2.21	87.72	91.32	5.62	2.93
Fruit and vegetables	7.46	10.16	5.66	4.84	73.94	74.46	12.94	10.54
Vegetable & animal oils	0.78	1.30	1.97	2.11	95.35	94.57	1.90	2.01
Dairy products	3.77	3.43	3.25	2.21	90.39	91.15	2.59	3.21
Grain mill, starches and starch products	2.13	2.39	2.72	3.18	90.22	90.39	4.93	4.04
Other food products	7.06	6.56	4.61	3.81	78.57	82.54	9.77	7.09
Animal feeds	2.69	3.44	3.15	2.21	91.97	91.51	2.19	2.84

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Food Industry	3.24	3.87	3.82	3.12	88.05	88.64	4.89	4.38
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Source: Computed from Annual Survey of Industries Data, CSO, New Delhi

From the above Table 3, it can be noticed that the percentage cost is highest in material consumed which accounts for more than 88 percent followed by cost of capital. This indicates that financing the procurement of raw materials costs more than any other cost. Despite the fact that majority investments are in the raw materials, the percentage varies across the group. The Vegetable and animal oil processing has highest percentage of expenses which accounts around 95 percent and least percentage expenses (around 1 percent) on wages and salaries across all group.

Figure 3: Cost expenses in Indian food processing industry

Source: Annual Survey of Industries, CSO, New Delhi

The Fig. 3 above reveals that the cost expenses have hitched up across all the categories. The highest increase is observed in wages and salaries with around three and half times increase and least increase is in energy expenses.

The Table 4 below indicates the performance based on technical and scale efficiency computed using DEAP (2.0) in Indian Food Processing Industry. The output value considered was based on value of product and by-product specified in Annual Survey of Industries, basically there are two assumptions while computing technical efficiency; Constant return to scale (CRS) and Variable return to scale (VRS).

Table 4: Technical and Scale Efficiency in Indian Food Processing Industry

Group	2008-2009			2017-2018		
	CRSTE	VRSTE	SCALE	CRSTE	VRSTE	SCALE
Meat and meat products	0.951	0.996	0.955	0.953	0.997	0.956
Sea food	0.843	0.883	0.955	0.916	0.922	0.993
Fruit and vegetables	0.601	0.817	0.736	0.587	0.751	0.782
Vegetable and animal oils	0.892	0.987	0.904	0.984	0.987	0.997
Dairy products	0.944	0.949	0.995	0.944	0.958	0.985
Grain mill, starches and starch products	0.879	0.880	0.999	0.867	0.997	0.870
Other food products	0.614	0.615	0.998	0.735	0.985	0.746
Animal feeds	0.970	0.975	0.995	0.982	0.998	0.984
Food Industry	0.850	0.893	0.952	0.873	0.954	0.915

Note: CRSTE = technical efficiency from CRS DEA

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$VRSTE$ = technical efficiency from VRS DEA

$SCALE$ = scale efficiency = $CRSTE/VRSTE$

The value of constant return to scale is equal to one indicates that the group increase in input leads to equivalent output. The value of Variable return to scale is equal to one indicates that the groups' average productivity remained constant with increasing production scale. The scale efficiency is obtained by dividing aggregate efficiency by technical efficiency. The technical efficiency of food processing industry was 0.850 and 0.893 for CRS and VRS models respectively during 2008-09 and has increased to 0.873 and 0.958 during 2017-18. However, the scale efficiency has seen a decrease from 0.952 to 0.915 indicating the optimal utilization processing units have decreased.

Table 5: Returns to Scale in Indian Food Processing Industry

Group	2008-2009	2017-2018
Meat and meat products	IRS	IRS
Sea food	IRS	IRS
Fruit and vegetables	IRS	IRS
Vegetable and animal oils	CRS	DRS
Dairy products	IRS	DRS
Grain mill, starches and starch products	IRS	DRS
Other food products	IRS	DRS
Animal feeds	IRS	CRS

Note: CRS=Constant Returns to Scale

IRS=Increasing Returns to Scale

DRS= Decreasing Returns to Scale

The Table 5 above indicates whether the returns have increased, decreased or remained constant over the years. During the year 2008-09, all groups in the food processing industry have shown increasing returns to scale except Vegetable and animal oils which had constant returns to scale. During the year 2017-18, the Meat and meat products, Sea food and Fruit and vegetables processing groups have shown increasing returns to scale. This designate that these groups worked towards effective utilization of inputs. On the other hand, Vegetable and animal oils, Dairy products, Grain mill, starches and starch products, Other food products and Animal feeds processing striving to achieve better results with fresh infusion of capital.

Table 6: Efficiency Change and Total Factor Productivity Change in Indian Food Processing Industry

Group	2008-2009		2017-2018	
	EFFCH	TFPCH	EFFCH	TFPCH
Meat and meat products	1.052	1.047	0.953	0.943
Sea food	1.052	1.047	1.033	1.022
Fruit and vegetables	1.093	1.088	0.893	0.884
Vegetable and animal oils	0.95	0.946	1.036	1.025
Dairy products	0.917	0.913	1.09	1.078
Grain mill, starches and starch products	0.955	0.951	1.031	1.02
Other food products	1.106	1.1	1.082	1.07
Animal feeds	1.002	0.997	1.029	1.018
Food Industry	1.014	1.009	1.017	1.006

Note: EFFCH=Efficiency Change

TFPCH= Total Factor Productivity Change

The Table 6 above presents the efficiency change and TFP change in various groups of Indian food processing industry based on Malmquist TFP index model. The output-based change is measured over 2008 to 2018 for a given level of inputs. The fluctuation in efficiency is attributed to either technological innovations or competent use of inputs. If the

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value index is greater than unity, it is regarded as progress, otherwise retrogress in productivity. The efficiency and TFP change for overall industry show decline during 2017-18 compared to 2008-09.

During the financial year 2017-18, all groups exhibit value more than one indicating positive change in efficiency except Meat and meat products and Fruit and vegetables processing firms. Accordingly, it is understood that unorganised sector of meat and fresh fruits and vegetables have greater demand over processed products in domestic market. Further, it also reveals that there is huge potential to invest in other groups of Indian food processing industry where the opportunity of value addition is high.

V. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The food processing industry in India is of significant importance since large population depends on farming for income generation, specifically rural areas. The study analyses the growth prospects of Indian food processing industry. The secondary data is collected from various issues of Annual survey of Industries report for ten years (2008 to 2018). The food processing industry is classified into eight groups: Meat and meat products, Sea food, Fruit and vegetables, Vegetable and animal oils, Dairy products, Grain mill starches & starch products, other food products and Animal feeds for the purpose of study. The Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) model is adopted to compute the efficiencies. The estimates of Malmquist productivity index is computed using Data Envelopment Analysis Program (DEAP) software (version 2.1) developed by Coelli (1996).

The overall number of factories in Food processing industries have increased by around 46 percent during 2008 to 2018. However, the total number of employees has shrunk by around 7 percent during the same decade. On the rationale grounds, technological innovations are held responsible because of which employees are substituted by automated machineries. Further, the first five year of analysis duration constitutes better growth compared to the second half in terms of number of factories as well as employment. The value addition in food processing industry has tremendously amplified over years. The significant contribution is found in other food products group which also engages highest number of employees across all groups.

The cost structure of the industry is analysed by divided into four categories; a) wages and salaries which represent the remuneration paid both to labours and managers b) Fuel consumed which includes energy generated to process in terms of petrol, diesel and electricity c) Material consumed which indicates inputs such as raw agricultural produce, chemicals and d) packaging and cost of capital which is sum of depreciation, interest and rent paid. Almost 88 percent of cost is involved in procurement of raw material. However, the cost expenses have increased by three and half times in wages and salaries.

In the performance front, it is observed that the technical efficiency of food processing industry has increased (both CRS and VRS) indicating enhancement in production frontier; while the scale efficiency has decreased indicating wastage of inputs. Further, during the year 2017-18, the Meat and meat products, Sea food and Fruit and vegetables processing groups have shown increasing returns to scale. On the other hand, Vegetable and animal oils, Dairy products, Grain mill, starches and starch products, Other food products and Animal feeds processing striving to achieve better results with fresh infusion of capital.

The output-based, Malmquist TFP index estimates are analysed to identify fluctuations in TFP change. The efficiency and TFP change for overall industry show decline during 2017-18 compared to 2008-09. Almost all groups exhibit improved efficiency except Meat and meat products and Fruit and vegetables processing firms. Accordingly, it is understood that unorganised sector of meat and fresh fruits and vegetables have greater demand over processed products in domestic market. From the above analysis, it can be concluded that there exists momentous opportunity to generate income by procuring quality raw materials to enhance the quality of product to meet standards and scaling down the wastage of inputs. This provides road to international markets and finally attracting investments which is prime agenda of any nation's economy.

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